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POSTER PRESENTATIONS

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ARE FUTURE HEALTHCARE PROFESSIONALS SUFFICIENTLY PREPARED TO PARTICIPATE IN PHARMACOVIGILANCE ACTIVITIES? A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY FROM THE AUTONOMOUS PROVINCE OF VOJVODINA, SERBIA

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Introduction: The ability to actively participate in pharmacovigilance activities is an important competency that future healthcare professionals should acquire. Considering this, the aim of this study was to assess pharmacovigilance knowledge and attitudes in a population of healthcare sciences students in the AP of Vojvodina, Serbia, using a newly developed and validated questionnaire.

Materials and methods: From February to July 2021, an observational cross-sectional study that included students of medicine, dentistry, pharmacy, and nursing science at three faculties in AP Vojvodina was conducted. The newly developed three-part *Questionnaire for Assessing Knowledge and Attitudes About Pharmacovigilance for*

Students of Healthcare Sciences, PVKAQ (I: Demographic Data Section, II: Pharmacovigilance Knowledge Test, PVKT, and III: Pharmacovigilance Attitude Questionnaire, PVAQ), was voluntarily and anonymously completed by 242 healthcare sciences students via the Google Forms platform, 211 of whom met the inclusion criteria for the study.

Results: After conducting a statistical analysis of the PVKT and PVAQ tests, it was found that both tests had good reliability values. The average score on the PVKT test was 9.14 (R=0-14; SD=2.65; Me=10), indicating that the respondents knew more than 50% of the correct answers. Those studying medicine had the highest average score on the PVKT (M=9.96; SD=1.81; Me=10). The average scores on the PAPV (assessing respondents' attitudes) and PAADR (assessing respondents' willingness) PVAQ subscales were 31.98 (R=7-35; SD=3.68; Me=33) and 43.12 (R=13-65; SD=10.63; Me=45), respectively. Students of nursing science had the highest PAPV score (M=32.84; SD=2.59; Me=34), while students of medicine had the highest PAADR score (M=46.69; SD=8.03; Me=47.5).

Table: The average scores of respondents in the PVKAQ questionnaire

PVKAQ section	Average Score	SD	Me
PVKT	9.14 (0-14)	2.65	10
PAPV (PVAQ)	31.98 (7-35)	3.68	33
PAADR (PVAQ)	43.12 (13-65)	10.63	45

Conclusions: A new questionnaire has been created and statistically tested to assess the knowledge and attitudes about pharmacovigilance among healthcare sciences students. The study found that students had a good level of knowledge about pharmacovigilance but were less likely to report adverse drug responses in the future.

Keywords: pharmacovigilance, healthcare sciences students, knowledge, attitudes